

Compactness in asymmetric quasi normed spaces

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Abstract

In this paper it is represented a study of precompact and compact subsets on asymmetric quasi normed spaces.

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1. Introduction

Definition 1.1. A function $p : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ is an *asymmetric quasi norm* on X if for every $x, y, z \in X$, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^+$ and $k \geq 1$:

- 1) $p(x) = p(-x) = 0 \Leftrightarrow x = 0$
- 2) $p(\lambda x) = \lambda p(x)$
- 3) $p(x + y) \leq k(p(x) + p(y))$.

For $k = 1$ the function is called the *asymmetric norm function*, and the pair (X, p) is called the asymmetric normed space. More information on this structure can be found in [1] and [2].

The function $p^{-1} : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ defined by $p^{-1}(x) = p(-x)$ is also an asymmetric quasi norm.

While the formula $p^s(x) = \max\{p(x), p^{-1}(x)\}$ gives a quasi norm on X .

Definition 1.2. A *quasi metric* on a set X is a function $d : X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ that satisfies:

- 1) $d(x, y) = d(y, x) = 0 \Leftrightarrow x = y$
- 2) $d(x + y) \leq d(x, z) + d(z, y)$, for every $x, y, z \in X$.

Each quasi metric d on X generates a topology $T(d)$ on X , that in general is a T_0 topology. The basic open sets can be defined as the d-balls:

$$B_d(x, r) = \{y \in X : d(x, y) < r\}, \quad x \in X, \quad r > 0.$$

An asymmetric quasi norm p on a linear space X induces the quasi metric d_p by means of the formula:

$$d_p(x, y) = p(y - x), \quad x, y \in X.$$

Thus the sets: $B_\varepsilon^p(0) = \{x \in X : p(x) < \varepsilon\}$, $\varepsilon > 0$, define a fundamental system of neighborhoods of zero for the topology $T(d_p)$, and for all $y \in X$, the sets $B_\varepsilon^p(y) = y + B_\varepsilon^p(0)$ define a fundamental system of neighborhoods of y (these sets are convex). Then we say that the pair (X, p) is an asymmetric quasi normed linear space.

Now let us deal that with the topologies induced by p, p^{-1}, p^s , we will write these symbols before the property we are referring if necessary; for instance, we will write p -compact set, or p^s -compact set to refer to compactness of a set with respect to the topology induced by p (resp. by p^s).

If the space (X, p^s) is complete, we say that (X, p) is a bi-Banach space (see [3]).

Denote by $B_{\leq, \varepsilon}^p$ the set:

$$B_{\leq, \varepsilon}^p(0) = \{x \in X : p(x) \leq \varepsilon\}, \quad \varepsilon > 0.$$

Let (X, p) an asymmetric quasi normed space and $x \in X$, denote by Ψ_x the set defined by:

$$\Psi_x = \{y \in X : d_p(x, y) = p(y - x) = 0\}.$$

In particular:

$$\Psi_0 = \{y \in X : d_p(0, y) = p(y) = 0\}.$$

Observe that Ψ_x is the closure of $\{x\}$ in (X, p^{-1}) .

Given a set $A \subset X$ of an asymmetric quasi normed space (X, p) (analogue Lemma 2 in [4]), we have that:

$$\bigcup_{x \in A} \Psi_x = A + \Psi_0$$

where:

$$A + \Psi_0 = \{z \in X : z = x + y, x \in A, y \in \Psi_0\}.$$

We have also that $B_{\varepsilon}^{p^s}(x) = B_{\varepsilon}^p(x) + \Psi_0, x \in X$ (see [4]) and if $A \subset X$ is an open set, then $A = A + \Psi_0$.

Definition 1.3. (Its analogue is in [4]) Let (X, p) be an asymmetric quasi normed space. We say it is *right-bounded* if there exists a real constant $r > 0$, such that:

$$rB_1^p(0) \subset B_1^{p^s}(0) + \Psi_0.$$

Note that the inclusion $B_{\varepsilon}^{p^s}(x) + \Psi_0 \subset B_{\varepsilon}^p(x)$ holds in any asymmetric quasi norm space (X, p) , for every $\varepsilon > 0$ and $x \in X$. In fact if $y \in B_{\varepsilon}^{p^s}(x) + \Psi_0$, then there are some $x_0 \in B_{\varepsilon}^{p^s}(x)$ and $z_0 \in \Psi_0$ such that $y = x_0 + z_0$. By the triangle inequality we have that $p(y - x) < \varepsilon$. Then $y \in B_{\varepsilon}^p(x)$.

2. Main results

Let (X, p) be an asymmetric quasi normed space.

Definition 2.1. A subset A of X is *p-bounded* if there is a positive constant M such that $p(x) \leq M$ for all $x \in A$. It is obvious that if a set A is p -bounded and p^{-1} -bounded, then A is p^s -bounded.

Definition 2.2. We say that a subset A of X is *p-precompact* if for all $\varepsilon > 0$ we can find a finite set of points $\{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ in A such that: $A \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^n B_{\varepsilon}^p(a_i)$.

We say that a subset A of an asymmetric quasi normed space (X, p) is *outside p-precompact* if for each $\varepsilon > 0$ there is a finite set $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ in X such that $A \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^n B_{\varepsilon}^p(x_i)$. Obviously if a set A is p -precompact, then it is outside p -precompact; the converse is not true in general, a p -convergent sequence is outside p -precompact but not necessarily p -precompact.

The relationship between p -precompactness and outside p -precompactness is given by the following proposition.

Proposition 2.3. Let (X, p) be an asymmetric quasi normed space. A subset A of X is p -precompact if and only if for all $\varepsilon > 0$ there is a finite set $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ in X such that $A \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^n B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^p(x_i)$ and $B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^{p^{-1}}(x_i) \cap A \neq \Phi$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$.

Proof. The direct implication is obvious by the definition of p -precompact set. To prove the converse fix a positive ε and choose a finite set $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ in X such that $A \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^n B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^p(x_i)$ and $B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^{p^{-1}}(x_i) \cap A \neq \Phi$ for some $k \geq 1$. Take $a_i \in B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^{p^{-1}}(x_i) \cap A$; we must prove that $B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^p(x_i) \subset B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^p(a_i)$. If $x \in B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^p(x_i)$, then:

$$p(x - a_i) \leq k(p(x - x_i) + p(x_i - a_i)) < k\left(\frac{\varepsilon}{2k} + p^{-1}(a_i - x_i)\right) = k\left(\frac{\varepsilon}{2k} + \frac{\varepsilon}{2k}\right) = \varepsilon.$$

Then the set A is p -precompact. ■

Proposition 2.4. Let (X, p) be an asymmetric quasi normed space then:

- (1) The finite sum and the finite union of p -precompact sets is p -precompact.
- (2) The convex hull of a p -precompact set is p -precompact.

Proof. (1) This result is an immediate consequence of the definition. We give the proof for the case of the sum of two p -precompact sets A_1 and A_2 . Let $\varepsilon > 0$. Take $\frac{\varepsilon}{2k}$ for some $k \geq 1$, and consider the sets $\{x_1^1, \dots, x_n^1\} \subset A_1$ and $\{x_1^2, \dots, x_m^2\} \subset A_2$ such that:

$$A_1 \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^n B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^p(x_i^1) \quad \text{and} \quad A_2 \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^m B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^p(x_i^2).$$

If $z \in A_1 + A_2$ then $z = z_1 + z_2$, with $z_1 \in A_1$ and $z_2 \in A_2$. There are elements x_i^1 and x_j^2 such that $p(z_1 - x_i^1) < \frac{\varepsilon}{2k}$ and $p(z_2 - x_j^2) < \frac{\varepsilon}{2k}$. Then:

$$p(z - (x_i^1 + x_j^2)) \leq k(p(z_1 - x_i^1) + p(z_2 - x_j^2)) < k\left(\frac{\varepsilon}{2k} + \frac{\varepsilon}{2k}\right) = \varepsilon.$$

Thus the set $\{x_i^1 + x_j^2; i = 1, \dots, n; j = 1, \dots, m\}$ define an adequate set of centers of p -balls of radius ε to cover the set $A_1 + A_2$.

For the proof of (2), let see A a p -precompact subset of X . For $\varepsilon > 0$, we can find a set of points of A , $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ such that $A \subset \{x_1, \dots, x_n\} + B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2}}^p(0)$. Denote by $\text{convex}(A)$ the convex hull of A ; we have:

$$\text{convex}(A) \subset \text{convex}(\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}) + B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2}}^p(0).$$

Note that since $\text{convex}(\{x_1, \dots, x_n\})$ is p^s -compact, then it is p -precompact. Thus we can define a set $\{y_1, \dots, y_n\}$ in $\text{convex}(\{x_1, \dots, x_n\})$ such that:

$$\text{convex}(\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}) \subset \{y_1, \dots, y_n\} + B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2}}^p(0).$$

Then we conclude that:

$$\text{convex}(A) \subset \{y_1, \dots, y_n\} + B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2}}^p(0) + B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2}}^p(0) \subset \{y_1, \dots, y_n\} + B_{\varepsilon}^p(0)$$

and confirm that $\text{convex}(A)$ is p -precompact. ■

Proposition 2.5. A subset A of (X, p) is p -precompact if and only if the p^{-1} -closure of A is p -precompact.

Proof. If A is p -precompact and $\varepsilon > 0$, $k \geq 1$, there is a finite set in A , $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ such that:

$$A \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^n B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^p(x_i) \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^n B_{\leq, \frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^p(x_i).$$

Note that the sets $B_{\leq, \frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^p(x_i)$ are p^{-1} -closed. Then:

$$\overline{A}^{p^{-1}} \subset \overline{\bigcup_{i=1}^n B_{\leq, \frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^p(x_i)}^{p^{-1}} \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^n \overline{B_{\leq, \frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^p(x_i)}^{p^{-1}} = \bigcup_{i=1}^n B_{\leq, \frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^p(x_i) \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^n B_{\leq, \varepsilon}^p(x_i).$$

Conversely: If $\overline{A}^{p^{-1}}$ is p -precompact, for $\varepsilon > 0$ and some $k \geq 1$, there is a finite subset of $\overline{A}^{p^{-1}}$, $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$, such that:

$$A \subset \overline{A}^{p^{-1}} \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^n \left(x_i + B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^p(0) \right).$$

We have that for every $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, $x_i \in \overline{A}^{p^{-1}}$. Then for a fixed index i there is some $a_i \in A$ such that:

$$p^{-1}(a_i - x_i) = p(x_i - a_i) < \frac{\varepsilon}{2k}.$$

Now let us prove that: $x_i + B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^p(0) \subset a_i + B_{\varepsilon}^p(0)$.

Let $y \in x_i + B_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2k}}^p(0)$. Then $p(y - x_i) < \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$ and:

$$p(y - a_i) \leq k(p(y - x_i) + p(x_i - a_i)) < k\left(\frac{\varepsilon}{2k} + \frac{\varepsilon}{2k}\right) = \varepsilon.$$

So we have A is p -precompact. ■

Let (X, p) be an asymmetric quasi normed space and $K \subset X$.

Then K is compact respect to the topology $T(d_p)$ induced by the asymmetric quasi norm p if and only if $K + \Psi_0$ is compact for the same topology (see [4]). An analogue proposition and its proof of the following proposition, for the case of the asymmetric norm is given in [5]

Proposition 2.6. Let (X, p) be an asymmetric quasi normed space. If K is a subset of X such that $K_0 \subset K \subset K_0 + \Psi_0$ where K_0 is p^s -compact, then K is p -compact.

Theorem 2.7. Let (X, p) be an asymmetric quasi normed space. Let K be a subset of X , then:

- (1) If (X, p) is a bi-Banach right-bounded space with constant $r=1$ and K is p -precompact set then there is a p^s -compact subset K_0 of X such that $K \subset K_0 + \Psi_0$.
- (2) If there is a p^s -precompact subset K_0 of X such that $K \subset K_0 + \Psi_0$ then K is outside p -precompact.

Proof. (1) *Step 1.* First we construct an special family of balls covering the set K in order to find an adequate p^s -compact set. By the definition of p -precompactness we have that for $\varepsilon = \frac{1}{4k}$ and $\varepsilon = \frac{1}{2k}$, $k \geq 1$:

$$K \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^{n_1} B_{\frac{1}{2k}}^p(x_i^1), \{x_1^1, \dots, x_{n_1}^1\} \subset K \text{ and } K \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^{n_2} B_{\frac{1}{4k}}^p(x_i^2), \{x_1^2, \dots, x_{n_2}^2\} \subset K.$$

It follows that for all $i = 1, \dots, n_2$, there is an index $j_i \in \{1, \dots, n_1\}$ such that $x_i^2 \in B_{\frac{1}{2k}}^p(x_{j_i}^1)$.

We also have that $B_{\frac{1}{2k}}^p(x_{j_i}^1) \subset B_{\frac{1}{2k}}^{p^s}(x_{j_i}^1) + \Psi_0$. Thus $x_i^2 = \bar{x}_i^2 + z$ with $\bar{x}_i^2 \in B_{\frac{1}{2k}}^{p^s}(x_{j_i}^1)$ and $z \in \Psi_0$.

If $y \in B_{\frac{1}{4k}}^p(x_i^2)$ then:

$$p(y - \bar{x}_i^2) \leq k(p(y - x_i^2) + p(z)) < k\left(\frac{1}{4k}\right) = \frac{1}{4}.$$

Thus $B_{\frac{1}{4k}}^p(x_i^2) \subset B_{\frac{1}{4k}}^p(\bar{x}_i^2)$, and $\left\{B_{\frac{1}{4k}}^p(\bar{x}_i^2) : i = 1, \dots, n_2\right\}$ defines a p -cover of K .

Following this construction for each $N \in \mathbb{N}$ we obtain a family $\{x_1^{-N}, \dots, x_{n_N}^{-N}\}$, such that for each $x_i^{-N}, i = 1, \dots, n_N$ there is $x_{j_i}^{-N-1}$ such that:

$$p^s\left(x_i^{-N} - x_{j_i}^{-N-1}\right) < \frac{1}{2^{N-1}}$$

and:

$$K \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^{n_N} B_{\frac{1}{2^N}}^p(x_i^{-N}).$$

Let $L = \left\{x_1^{-1}, x_2^{-1}, \dots, x_{n_1}^{-1}, x_1^{-2}, \dots, x_{n_2}^{-2}, \dots\right\}$, with $x_i^{-1} = x_i^1$ for $i = 1, \dots, n_1$. We will prove first that L is p^s -precompact.

Let $\varepsilon > 0$ and consider some $N \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\frac{1}{2^{N-2}} < \frac{\varepsilon}{k}$ for some $k \geq 1$. We omit the subindexes for the aim of clarity. Take some $\bar{x}^{-m} \in L$; then we have two cases:

Case 1: $m \leq N$. Then we have:

$$\bar{x}^{-m} \in B_{\varepsilon}^{p^s}(\bar{x}^{-m}) \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^{n_m} B_{\varepsilon}^{p^s}(x_i^{-m}) \subset \bigcup_{l=1}^N \bigcup_{i=1}^{n_l} B_{\varepsilon}^{p^s}(x_i^{-l}).$$

Case 2: $m > N$, fixed $\bar{x}^{-m}$ there is an element $\bar{x}^{-m-1}$ such that $p^s(\bar{x}^{-m} - \bar{x}^{-m-1}) < \frac{1}{2^{m-1}}$.

In the same way there is $\bar{x}^{-m-2}$ such that $p^s(\bar{x}^{-m-1} - \bar{x}^{-m-2}) < \frac{1}{2^{m-2}}$ and if we continue like this we obtain

$\bar{x}^{-N}$ such that $p^s(\bar{x}^{-N} - \bar{x}^{-N-1}) < \frac{1}{2^{N-1}}$. Then we have:

$$p^s(\bar{x}^{-l} - \bar{x}^{-l-1}) < \frac{1}{2^{l-1}} \text{ for } l = N, \dots, m.$$

Thus:

$$\begin{aligned} p^s(\bar{x}^{-m} - \bar{x}^{-N}) &\leq k \left(p^s(\bar{x}^{-m} - \bar{x}^{-m-1}) + p^s(\bar{x}^{-m-1} - \bar{x}^{-m-2}) + \dots + p^s(\bar{x}^{-N+1} - \bar{x}^{-N}) \right) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2^{m-1}} + \frac{1}{2^{m-2}} + \dots + \frac{1}{2^N} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2^{N-1}} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^j} \right) = \frac{1}{2^{N-1}}. \end{aligned}$$

Then we conclude $p^s(\bar{x}^{-m} - \bar{x}^{-N}) \leq k \frac{1}{2^{N-1}} < k \frac{\varepsilon}{k} = \varepsilon$, that is: $\bar{x}^{-m} \in B_\varepsilon^{p^s}(\bar{x}^{-N}) \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^{n_N} B_\varepsilon^{p^s}(x_i)$.

Therefore $L \subset \bigcup_{l=1}^N \bigcup_{i=1}^{n_l} B_\varepsilon^{p^s}(x_i)$ which proves that L is p^s -precompact, thus $\bar{L}^{p^s}$ is p^s -compact.

Step 2. Let $K_0 = \bar{L}^{p^s}$. We must prove that $K \subset K_0 + \Psi_0$.

If $x \in K$, for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, there is some $\bar{x}^{-n}$ of the corresponding family obtained in the previous step (we omit the indexes since there is no confusion) such that:

$$x \in B_{\frac{1}{2^n}}^{p^s}(\bar{x}^{-n}) = B_{\frac{1}{2^n}}^{p^s}(\bar{x}^{-n}) + \Psi_0.$$

Then for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, there are $\bar{y}^{-n} \in B_{\frac{1}{2^n}}^{p^s}(\bar{x}^{-n})$ and $z^n \in \Psi_0$ such that $x = \bar{y}^{-n} + z^n$.

Consider the sequence $\{\bar{x}^{-n}\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset \bar{L}^{p^s}$; since $\bar{L}^{p^s}$ is p^s -compact there is a subsequence $\{\bar{x}^{-n_l}\}_l$, p^s -convergent to $x_0 \in \bar{L}^{p^s}$.

Let us now prove that $p(x - x_0) = 0$. For a positive ε there is some index l_0 such that for all $l \geq l_0$, we have:

$$p^s(\bar{x}^{-n_l} - x_0) < \frac{\varepsilon}{2}, \text{ note that: } p^s(\bar{x}^{-n_l} - \bar{y}^{-n_l}) < \frac{1}{2^{n_l}}.$$

If we choose l_1 such that $\frac{1}{2^{n_l}} < \frac{\varepsilon}{2k}$ for $l \geq l_1$ and some $k \geq 1$, and consider $l_2 = \max\{l_0, l_1\}$, then for all $l \geq l_2$ we have:

$$p(x - x_0) \leq k \left(p(x - \bar{y}^{-n_l}) + p(\bar{y}^{-n_l} - \bar{x}^{-n_l}) + p(\bar{x}^{-n_l} - x_0) \right)$$

$$\leq k \left(0 + p^s(\bar{y}^{n_i} - \bar{x}^{n_i}) + p^s(\bar{x}^{n_i} - x_0) \right) < k \left(\frac{1}{2^{n_i}} + \frac{\varepsilon}{2k} \right) < k \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{2k} + \frac{\varepsilon}{2k} \right) = \varepsilon.$$

Since this can be done for every $\varepsilon > 0$, we obtain that $p(x - x_0) = 0$ so $x - x_0 \in \Psi_0$. We conclude that:

$$x \in \bar{L}^{p^s} + \Psi_0 = K_0 + \Psi_0.$$

End of the proof for (1).

For the proof of (2), choose some $\varepsilon > 0$. Since K_0 is p^s -precompact, there is a finite set $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ in K_0 such that $K_0 \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^n B_\varepsilon^{p^s}(x_i)$. Then (see [4]):

$$K_0 \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^n B_\varepsilon^{p^s}(x_i) + \Psi_0 = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \left(B_\varepsilon^{p^s}(x_i) + \Psi_0 \right) \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^n B_\varepsilon^p(x_i).$$

That is clear that K is outside p -precompact. ■

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